

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE UZBEK STATE - THE STATE OF THE TREASURERS

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Abstract: Origin of Ghaznavids and relations with Karakhanids, topics-relationships, binary relations and their matrix, the state of Ghaznavids during the time of Mahmud Ghaznavid, socio-economic life in the state of Ghaznavids, State administration system.

Key words. The Greatest Limits of the Ghaznavid Empire, 1030, Mahmud During the Ghaznavid period, Capital Ghazna (977–1163), Lahore (1163–1186)
Language(s), Persian (state, palace), Turkish Dini Sunni.

We cannot accept some of the current views of Soviet historiography regarding the emergence and rise of the Ghaznavids as a political force. It is not an exaggeration to say that before, they tried to show the Ghaznavids (therefore, their time) mainly in a negative light. For example, the Ghazna province, where this dynasty was founded, was interpreted as a convenient place for the "rebellious Turkish commanders" to gain wealth, and the history of the Ghaznavid dynasty, which came into force here and is known by the name of this city (province), is also interesting. or stated to have arisen and operated for the same purpose. In fact, it is a historical event there are several reasons. First of all, it is good that after Ismail Samani, a person who is mature in all respects, who can conduct politics at a high level, has grown up among the Samanis. As a result, the Somanites depended more on existing political laws than on their internal, i.e. dynastic, capabilities. The political environment at this time was unimaginable

without influential military commanders. The increase in the political activity of the forces in the Ghazna region is once in a generation the rise to the level of the dynasty is also in the name of the great military commanders depends, we will see clearly below. It is not a question of whether such a situation is good or bad, regardless of the consequences, such a situation happened, and it is useful in every way to know it. There are enough testimonies that the Ghaznavid dynasty did not arise out of some kind of "predation", but in the environment of socio-political relations in the region. After the death of Samani ruler Abdumalik in 961, the ministers installed the deceased's son on the throne. In the words of the source, Alptegin, who "deserves praise for the Soman family, has done services and led the way as viceroy and commander-in-chief", opposes this. 3. In this way, the opposition between the archons of the state and Alptegin will intensify and reach its peak. The army commander leaves Bukhara. even after that, the conflicts did not end, and in the end, a clash took place between the Alptegin and Bukhara armies, and the Bukhara army was defeated. Alptegin, who cut ties with the Somanids and Movarounnahr, established his rule in the Ghazna region. After his death (963), Amir Ishaq ibn Alptegin, Amir Bilgategin, Amir Piri, and Amir Sabuktegin ruled the treasury. 4. It is Sobuqtegin who founded the Ghaznavid political dynasty. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that Alptegin took the first significant step in the transformation of the treasury into one of the political centers of the region. As mentioned, despite the fact that Alptegin broke off contact with the Somanites,

Somanites embodied in the treasury and expanding political and military who have always felt the need for strength. A clear proof of this is the meeting between Sobuqtegin and Samani Nuh III (976-997) around Kesh (in which Sobuqtegin promised to support Nuh), or else in 994, one of the fiercest enemies of the Samanis, Abu It can be seen through the main role played by Sobuqtegin in the defeat of Ali Simjuri. Sobuqtegin's reputation was so high in recent years that

he was known with the honorary title of "defender of religion and state (Nasir ad-din wa ad-dawla)". Recognition of the Ghaznavids as both official and practical political power dates back to 996.

The ruler who increased the power and fame of the Ghaznavids is actually this same Mahmud. For example, during his reign (998-1030), regions and places such as Khorezm, Khorasan, Seistan, Kabul, Ghazna, North India were under the control of the Ghaznavids. After Mahmud's death, his son Muhammad took the throne, although he had an older son (Mas'ud). According to the commentary of the sources written at that time, Mahmud bequeathed the throne to his younger son Muhammad and told him: "Do not go into conflict with your brother Mas'ud, if he opposes you, do not fight, (invalid) perish." "You are a child." Indeed, soon there will be an opposition between Mas'ud and Muhammad. Contemporary historians also recognize that Mas'ud was superior to Muhammad. So, this year Mas'ud will take the throne. As we've seen many times before, it's usually something in the history of the dynasty, the politician, who is in a certain sense fluffy, always "in love", appeared on the stage of history once. The Ghaznavids were no exception. Therefore, it is correct to say that the era of Mas'ud (1030-1041) was mainly the years of attempts to preserve the results achieved by the efforts of Mahmud. First, in 1034, Khorezm left the sphere of influence of the Ghaznavids. Secondly, the rise of another political dynasty in Khorasan, the Seljuks, coincided with the same period of Mas'ud.

Speaking about the role played by the Ghaznavids in the cultural life of the region, the space and time in which they ruled played an important role in the development and universal achievements of science and culture of the 11th century. Of course, the reason for this can be attributed to the fact that the region has become a center of traditional science and culture. At the same time, in our opinion, the relationship of the representatives of the Ghaznavid dynasty to this field, the factor of personal capabilities did not play a small role in this. For

example, Mahmud Ghaznavi perfectly knew Persian, Arabic and even Pahlavi languages in addition to Turkish, he wrote poetry. That is probably why the centers ruled by Mahmud and the Ghaznavids in general were at the forefront of the cultural environment of their time. Famous poets, historians, scientists such as Farruhi, Unsuri, Manuchehri, Utbi, Gardizi, Bayhaqi Nasir Khysrav worked under the patronage of Ghaznavids. Our great ancestor Abu Raikhan Beruni studied science in the palace of the Ghaznavids and wrote many of his famous works, including "India", "Geodesia", "Famous People of Khorezm", "Masud's Law", "Mineralogy", "Saydana". wrote in Ghazna. The name of another famous cultural figure is related to the Ghaznavids. The word is about Abulqasim Fardavsi. Firdausi, who is considered one of the genius poets of Persian literature, to everyone After writing the well-known work "Shahnoma" in more than thirty years, he presented it to Sultan Mahmud according to the rules of that time. Mahmud had to reward and honor the poet for this huge poetic work (consisting of more than 60,000 verses). But he doesn't.

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